

40, and 60 days after transplanting.

The results of 2 years' (1974-75 and 1975-76) experiments indicate that all fungicides reduced the infection and increased yields (see table). Edifenphos

was most effective. Similar findings were also reported by Mohanti and Dash in 1971 and Subramanian and Ramaswamy in 1973. Miltox and blue copper were also good.

exposed to natural infection in the blast nursery. Ten days later the number of blast-infected plants and their lesion numbers were recorded.

With artificial inoculation disease incidence was greatest on KTH 17 (see table). The percentage of infection on this variety was highest (44.5%) on Bulacan phosphorus-deficient soil. Disease incidence ranged from 0 to 4% on Tetep and from 0 to 9% on IR442. I-2017 was not pathogenic on Carreon, which remained disease-free regardless of soil type.

Under natural infection, IR442 exhibited greater disease incidence in different soils than Tetep or KTH 17. That was expected because IR442 was used as the spreader source of inoculum in the blast nursery and most of the fungus populations present were pathogenic on it. KTH 17 produced more lesions than IR442 and Tetep with artificial inoculation in different soil types but in the blast nursery IR442 had more lesions than either KTH 17 or Tetep. Carreon remained disease-free in both instances, suggesting varietal differences in blast reaction.

Under natural conditions, disease incidence was high in Bulacan potassium-deficient, Malinao iron-toxic, and Pangil peat soil (see table). Disease incidence in susceptible varieties was greater on those soils, and least in the San Pablo zinc-deficient soil. That could be due to

Rice blast incidence in different soil types

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The evidence indicating increased blast susceptibility of rice when the soil nitrogen content is high seems conclusive, although the disease severity varies with other soil and climatic factors. The ratio of one element to another and the physical and chemical properties of the soil may play an important role in disease development. Numerous experiments from different countries have indicated that high soil nitrogen increases blast severity regardless of available phosphorus or potassium. That indicates that the influence of other elements is not significant. The influence of nitrogen on blast disease development under different soil conditions was evaluated to determine if varietal reactions to the

disease were affected.

Seven soils were obtained from various Philippine sites and designated by location as Malinao (Fe toxicity), Bulacan (K deficiency), Pangil (P deficiency), San Pablo (Zn deficiency), Pangil peat, Luisiana (P deficiency), and Maahas clay (normal check). The rice varieties used were Carreon, Tetep, IR442, and KTH 17. Carreon is resistant and the latter three varieties are highly susceptible to blast fungus isolate I-2017.

The soils were placed in plastic trays and 5 g ammonium sulfate was incorporated into each. Seeds were sown in four randomized rows. The plants were inoculated in the dew chamber with blast fungus isolate I-2017 that had been grown on prune agar for 18 days. At 24 hours after inoculation, the plants were transferred to the glasshouse (20-36°C) where a humidifier provided dew. Seven days after inoculation disease incidence was scored and the lesions (Types 3 and 4) on the infected plants were counted. Another set of varieties grown in trays with the different soil types were

Disease incidence and severity on four rice varieties in different soil types. IRRI, 1979.^a

Soil, disorder, series	Inoculated with I-2017								Natural infection							
	Carreon		Tetep		IR442		KTH 17		Carreon		Tetep		IR442		KTH 17	
	DI (%)	L/L	DI (70)	L/L	DI (%)	L/L	DI (%)	L/L	DI (%)	L/L	DI (%)	L/L	DI (%)	L/L	DI (%)	L/L
Bulacan (K deficient), Buonavista sandy clay loam	0	0	2.5	0	0	0	44.4	0.9	0	0	11	0.2	89	4.0	57	1.0
Maahas clay (normal), Lipa loam	0	0	2.5	0.3	5.5	0.4	34.5	2.7	0	0	22	0.2	92	4.9	52	1.7
Malinao (Fe toxicity), Malinao fine sandy loam	0	0	0	0	7	0.2	19.0	0.8	0	0	4.5	0	91	4.2	48	1.3
Pangil peat - Histosol from Pangil, Laguna	0	0	0	0	9	0	16.5	0.7	0	0	11.5	9.0	89	2.5	23	0.6
Luisiana (P deficient), Luisiana clay loam	0	0	4	0.5	2.5	0	12.5	1.0	0	0	13.5	0.5	78	2.3	24	0.5
Pangil (P deficient), Paete clay loam	0	0	3	0	4.0	0.3	10.0	1.0	0	0	14.0	0.3	89	2.7	31	0.9
San Pablo (Zn deficient) Lipa loam	0	0	0	0	4.5	0	8.0	0.9	0	0	8.0	0	51	1.6	11	0.7

^aDI = disease incidence, L/L = mean number of lesions per leaf.

the severe yellowing and stunting of the seedlings, but seedling growth was similar in Pangil peat soil, where disease incidence was greater.

The difference in disease severity may be due to the available soil nutrients that affect the plant tissues and the biochemistry of the host. Nutritional factors change the host's growing status,

cell structure, and chemical composition. The soil chemistry may affect pathogenesis, resulting in effects on disease incidence and severity. Plant nutrients required for pathogenesis are affected by the availability of soil nutrients that control plant growth and vigor and influence the plants' resistance to blast. Different varieties may respond

differently to the same nutritional environment, as demonstrated by Carreon, KTH 17, and IR442. The effect of excess or deficient essential elements in the soil on disease incidence and severity appears to depend on the combination of such elements as well as on the host and the pathogen. ■

Pest management and control INSECTS

Flight activities of brown planthopper, whitebacked planthopper, and their predator *C. lividipennis* in Malaysia

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The largest outbreak of the whitebacked planthopper (WBPH) *Sogatella furcifera* reported in Malaysia occurred in the Muda Irrigation Scheme in June 1979. It established the need for continuous surveillance of the pest. Light traps are an efficient device for monitoring the

planthoppers and some of their natural enemies. The light trap consists of a kerosene pressure lamp suspended about 1.8 m over a basin of water. Light traps were set in the Crop Protection building in Telok Chengai to study the flight activities of WBPH and the brown planthopper (BPH) and their predator *Cyrtorhinus lividipennis* at half-hour intervals from 1830 to 2300 hours.

Data from catches during 13 nights were analyzed. The percentage catch for each of the three insects was

calculated (see figure). Flight activities begin after 1900 hours, when the Kedah sky darkens. The main activity for all 3 insects appears to occur from 1930 to 2000 hours. Both WBPH and BPH continue to be active until 2100 hours. *C. lividipennis* is most active from 1930 to 2000 hours. The study indicated that light traps must be lighted only from 1900 to 2200 hours to monitor the BPH and WBPH in the Muda Irrigation Scheme. ■

Catch (%)

Effect of depth of submergence on incidence of bacterial blight and white grub infestation in transplanted rice

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Water submergence was conducive to the spread of bacterial blight caused by *Xanthomonas oryzae*, but it effectively checked white grub infestation in transplanted IR24 in a field experiment at Pantnagar, India.

The disease incidence in the deep submergence treatment was significantly higher than that in the saturation and rainfed treatments, but similar to that in shallow submergence (see table).

White grub infestation decreased with increasing depth of submergence. Significantly fewer plants were damaged